

Impact of Channel Provisioning Strategies in the Transient Resiliency of SuperC+L-band Networks

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Abstract—Optical networks are a key building block of today’s telecommunications infrastructure. As fundamental limits in spectral efficiency are getting closer, there is a renewed need to cater for more spectrum in these networks to meet the ever-growing capacity requirements. A cost-effective way to achieve this while relying on the existing fiber infrastructure is to exploit the SuperC+L transmission band. However, in these systems, the impact of power transients on the resilience of established services can be significantly higher. This paper introduces a framework to design and simulate the operation of a wideband optical network and to estimate the impact of power transients. Simulation results obtained on a reference transport network highlight the impact of the selected channel provisioning strategies on the resiliency of established services to power transients, providing insight into the trade-off between aggressive (optical margin) provisioning and reduced service impact of transients.

I. INTRODUCTION

Increasing global Internet traffic and the expected explosion in artificial intelligence (AI) applications will propel optical network capacities to new levels. As coherent transmission technologies mature and single-mode fiber (SMF) capacity approaches theoretical limits, spatial division multiplexing (SDM) [1], multi-band transmission (MBT) [2], and super bands [3] promise to support future capacity demands. SDM relies on using parallel spatial paths to transport information. It can be implemented using multi-fiber, multi-core fibers, multi-mode fibers, or few-mode fibres [1]. MBT seeks to optimize the usage of the low-loss spectrum of existing fiber infrastructure by deploying additional amplification bands beyond the C-band. Superbands enhance optical amplifier bandwidth from the typical 4.8 THz up to 6.1 THz, thereby increasing transmission bandwidth without incurring extra costs for amplifiers or fan-in/fan-out devices.

Studies suggest that expanding transmission bandwidth through MBT or superbands is a viable approach to postpone fiber deployments, particularly when deployment costs are high. However, in scenarios with low fiber deployment costs, MBT solutions become less attractive due to reduced system spectral efficiency (SE) resulting from the characteristics of new devices, increased fiber attenuation, and additional losses from fan-in/fan-out devices at each amplification site [4].

The design and operation of optical networks with broader bandwidth transmission systems pose additional complexities. One key factor is the heightened interdependency among transmitted channels in these systems due to the stimulated

Raman scattering (SRS) effect. SRS, a nonlinear phenomenon, transfers optical power from higher to lower frequencies. While it remains relatively weak in C-band transmission (typically 4 to 4.8 THz), SRS becomes more pronounced in wider bandwidths, achieving maximum efficiency at a frequency offset of approximately 13 THz. Additionally, more sophisticated physical layer models, such as the well-established Generalized Gaussian Noise (GGN) model [5], and a few selected others [6], are necessary to account for frequency-dependent parameters and the impact of SRS accurately.

An overlooked aspect of the SRS effect is that it exacerbates power variations (transients) experienced by surviving channels of a link fault, potentially leading to outages. These SRS-induced power transients worsen as transmission bandwidth broadens [7] and have been experimentally characterized [8]. This work evaluates the impact of the provisioning strategies utilized to set up optical channels on the robustness of services against SRS-induced power transients in wideband optical networks. The paper is structured as follows. Section II describes the leading causes of SRS-induced power transients. Section III covers physical layer modelling, the network simulation framework, the employed channel provisioning strategies, and the SRS-induced power transient simulation framework. Finally, Sections IV and V present the simulation results and draw the main conclusions, respectively.

II. POWER TRANSIENTS

In optical wavelength division multiplexed (WDM) C-band systems, power transients caused by link faults or network reconfigurations are well-documented. Researchers have explored various strategies to mitigate their impact [9], [10]. In WDM networks, different wavelengths traverse distinct paths, and when the power of specific wavelengths changes abruptly (e.g., due to a fault), cross saturation in erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFAs) induces power transients in surviving optical channels (OChs) [9]. These power transients occur at high speeds, and the response time needed to protect against such error bursts can be orders of magnitude higher than the typical dynamic time scale associated with EDFA control. Consequently, surviving lightpaths may experience error bursts if the received optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) falls below the forward error correcting (FEC) limit [10].

Fig. 1: (a) Pre- and (b) post-fault power spectrum profile at the input of the links in an example network.

A. The SRS Effect

SRS introduces interdependencies between wavelengths in MBT systems and contributes to power transients during link failures. Consider Fig. 1, which illustrates power variations resulting from a link fault in MBT systems. Two sets of channels traverse the same path from nodes C to F: 1) higher-frequency channels (in red) from node A to node F, and 2) lower-frequency channels (in blue) from node B to node F. Amplifiers are set to compensate for channel losses, including SRS-induced power transfer from red to blue channels (Fig. 1a). If a fiber cut occurs in the link from node B to node C, only surviving red channels continue between nodes C and F. However, the loss experienced by red channels after the fault is reduced because no power transfer occurs from red channels to blue channels post-fault. Given that the amplifiers are configured to compensate for a more significant loss than the channels experience, the difference between the channel input power at every link before the fault (shown by the red dashed line in Fig. 1b) and after the fault increases for some channels. This difference is more pronounced for longer shared paths, accumulating at each span. Assuming the amplifiers are optimally set before the fault, this power variation may impact the channels' quality of transmission (QoT).

To highlight the importance of this effect on MBT systems, Fig. 2 shows the variation of output power per carrier and of the generalized signal-to-noise ratio (GSNR) of the SuperC+L MBT system described in Section III after transmission along five spans of 75 km of SSMF resulting from dropping the entire SuperC band while keeping the gain and tilt of L-band amplifiers unchanged. The optical power of surviving carriers

Fig. 2: Variation of GSNR and received power per carrier of the SuperL-band when dropping the entire SuperC-band in a link comprising five spans of 75 km.

is reduced by as much as 7.4 dB, while the GSNR is impacted by 11.5 dB in the worst OCh.

It is worth noting that power transients resulting from link faults can sometimes enhance the transmission quality of surviving channels. Consider this scenario: after a fault, neighboring channels around channel i vanish, reducing non-linear interference (NLI) noise. However, the primary channels responsible for SRS effects on channel i remain, maintaining the SRS effect and the amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise. As a result, even though the input power of channel i is no longer optimal post-fault, it may still exhibit better GSNR than before the fault occurred.

The example above showcases the potential effects of a somewhat worst-case scenario in which many channels share the same path. In real networks, channel distribution is normally more dispersed and dependent on several factors, such as the traffic pattern and the routing and spectrum assignment (RSA) strategy. Hence, the chances of one entire amplification band being dropped because of a single link fault are small because such an event corresponds to a failure affecting only the amplifier of one band, which is typically less frequent than fiber cuts (impacting all channels in the affected fiber).

Another source of power transients in MBT systems is optical restoration. Unlike link faults, where channels vanish, optical restoration involves rerouting or reconfiguring channels in response to a failure. If executed too rapidly, these restored channels can disrupt the EDFA response or impact running channels via SRS, with effects similar to link faults but in the opposite direction. However, restoration can be phased in, and amplifiers may be preemptively adjusted because restoration is a controlled event.

B. Mitigation Strategies

The two main strategies to mitigate SRS-induced power transients are: 1) noise loading [11] and 2) margin stacking. Noise loading consists of maintaining the link power profile stable by anchoring power over specific frequency ranges or phasing ASE noise in substitution of failed channels. The first noise-loading approach can be attained by allocating a specific

subset of channels to this objective. Since these channels are always present, this scheme can reliably reduce the impact of power transients. However, these channels are assumed to be dedicated to this task and do not carry traffic, which reduces the overall system capacity. The second approach involves deploying ASE noise sources at each node that can be quickly activated to replace the missing channels at egress links. Although this scheme does not compromise system capacity, its effectiveness is conditioned to the time it takes between the channels being lost and the shaped ASE noise replacing them. All noise-loading approaches increase the complexity and cost of the line system.

Margin stacking during service provisioning consists of guaranteeing that every optical channel established in the network has sufficient margin to withstand SRS effects from a link failure in the current/forecasted network state. Although this approach avoids deploying specific hardware to avoid/mitigate power transients, it has several shortcomings. Firstly, estimating the required margin for a given channel is difficult since it implies a detailed simulation of possible failure scenarios for the current or target network state. Secondly, once an optical channel is provisioned with enough margin, restrictions may need to be enforced when provisioning future channels since certain (e.g., not forecasted) network states may not be compatible with the margin used in the already established channels. Thirdly, margin stacking tends to reduce SE and, consequently, requires deploying a higher number of optical interfaces to satisfy the traffic demand set [7].

Determining the most suitable transient mitigation strategy/strategies to adopt in a network exploiting the SuperC+L-band requires gaining insight into the expected impact of power transients due to the SRS effect in realistic network conditions. Achieving this demands considering the different steps and involved decisions of network design and operation, as well as simulating failure scenarios. For instance, it is important to understand how the provisioning strategy employed, which includes determining the eligibility criteria to use a given channel format over a specific routing path and the spectrum assignment (SA) algorithm used, can result in an increase/decrease of robustness to power transients in SuperC+L-band networks.

III. SIMULATION SETUP AND FRAMEWORK

The following subsections give details about the numerical simulations performed to evaluate the consequences of different SA strategies on the SRS-induced power transients caused by link faults in a SuperC+L-band system. They cover the physical layer modelling and QoT estimation, the network simulation framework, the channel provisioning strategies, and the SRS-induced power transient simulation framework.

A. Physical Layer Modelling

A disaggregated abstraction of the physical layer is considered in this work, i.e., each network element introduces a power gain or loss and possibly some amount of Gaussian disturbance. In dispersion uncompensated coherent-transmission

Fig. 3: Normalized Raman gain profile.

systems, the impact of nonlinear fiber transmission is well approximated as additive Gaussian noise in lightpaths with sufficient accumulated chromatic dispersion [12], therefore validating the GN approximation for NLI. Consequently, the QoT of an OCh can be estimated using the GSNR, which includes the effect of the additive Gaussian disturbances introduced by the optical amplifiers (ASE) and the nonlinear interference due to the self- and cross-channel nonlinear crosstalk resulting from optical fiber propagation. In this case, the GSNR of channel i after transmission along one fiber span s is given by (1), where P_i^s is the output power, $P_i^{ASE,s}$ is the accumulated ASE noise and $P_i^{NLI,s}$ is the power of accumulated nonlinear effects of channel i in span s . The same approach is followed in the open source Python library GNPpy, where it was shown that this is a suitable metric for the QoT estimation in modern coherent multilevel-modulated uncompensated WDM optical transmission systems [13].

$$GSNR_i^s = \frac{P_i^s}{P_i^{ASE,s} + P_i^{NLI,s}} \quad (1)$$

The GSNR of channel i at the end of an OCh ($GSNR_i^{Rx}$) is calculated as the inverse of the sum of the inverse of the GSNR in each network element in its path (transceiver, ROADM and fiber span). The transceiver OSNR ($OSNR_{Tx}$) is assumed to be 40 dB [14]. A colorless, directionless, contentionless (CDC) ROADM architecture is assumed. It comprises 1×32 wavelength selective switches (WSSs) at each degree and 8×6 multicast switches (MCS) as add/drop structures. The insertion losses of WSSs and MCSs are modeled based on commercially available devices.

The transmission of 120-GBd (R_S) signals in a 150-GHz spectral grid of a SuperC+L-band system is assumed. The SuperL-band supports 36 channels (184.8 THz to 190.3 THz), while the SuperC-band has up to 40 channels (190.6 THz to 196.7 THz). The EDFAs are modeled by a constant noise figure (NF) of 6 dB for gain values larger than 20 dB and 8 dB for gain values smaller than 14 dB. The NF is linearly interpolated for gain values between 14 and 20 dB. All deployed fiber is standard single mode fiber (SSMF) modeled by a nonlinear coefficient of $1.07 \text{ W}^{-1}/\text{km}$, a dispersion parameter of 16.8 ps/nm/km at 1550 nm, a dispersion slope of $0.058 \text{ ps/nm}^2/\text{km}$,

Topological Characterization	
#ROADMs	25
#Links/OMSs	86
#Spans	222
Avg span length	75.5 km

Fig. 4: Japan network topology and main characteristics.

and an attenuation coefficient of 0.21 dB/km. Additionally, splice losses of 0.01 dB/km, input/output connector losses of 0.25 dB and a frequency-offset-dependent Raman gain profile (Fig. 3) are considered.

B. Network Topology and Traffic Pattern

The impact of SRS-induced power transients is analyzed using a Japanese reference transport network, illustrated and characterized in Fig. 4. This reference network is based on the Japan Photonic Network Model (JPNM) defined in [15].

Traffic generation using a uniform spatial distribution is assumed to simulate network operation. Client traffic demands consist of 100GbE and 400GbE. Random traffic generation assumes approximately the same traffic volume from both client types (i.e., when a new client traffic demand is generated, it is $4\times$ more likely to be 100GbE than 400GbE). For each target average traffic load offered to the network, 20 independent traffic sets are generated and routed over the network. Hence, the capacity and interface count results presented in Section IV are always the average value of 20 independent runs.

C. Channel Provisioning Framework

In this work, the end-to-end QoT of an already provisioned or to-be-established OCh over a given physical path, using a specific channel format and frequency slot i , is assessed via the residual margin (RM), which is defined as:

$$RM_i = GSNR_i^{Rx} - SNR_{req} - M_{sys}, \quad (2)$$

where SNR_{req} is the required signal-to-noise ratio for the target channel format for a given receiver input power and M_{sys} is an additional margin to account for system penalties, namely penalties from filter cascading and polarization dependent losses [16]. The optical interfaces available to provision optical channels are assumed to be coherent pluggable interfaces based on the OpenZR+ specifications [14], but (1) scaled to

TABLE I: Coherent pluggable interface characteristics.

Modulation Format	Data Rate [Gb/s]	SNR_{req} [dB]	CD tolerance [ns/nm]
16QAM	800	16	30
8QAM	600	13	50
QPSK	400	8	60

120 Gbd and (2) with improved specs in a few key parameters. Table I summarizes the three modulation formats supported and, for each one, the data rate provided, the SNR_{req} and the chromatic dispersion (CD) tolerance.

This work's network design and operation process closely mimics real transport networks' planning and provisioning stages. Firstly, the baseline optical performance is determined by considering the worst-case impact of NLI in each span since it is impossible to accurately forecast the power profile (depending on future traffic demands, RSA algorithm, etc.). This means considering fully loaded spans, i.e., with 76 channels present in the SuperC+L-band. Hence, the GSNR for every frequency slot and every span of the network is optimized under this end-of-life (EOL) condition and by finding each amplifier's best gain and tilt, which is particularly more complex in wideband systems [17]. This work considers two different span optimization objectives: maximize the average $GSNR_i$ (MaxAv-GSNR) and maximize the lowest $GSNR_i$ (MaxLow-GSNR). The output of this first stage is used to validate the feasibility of potential OChs when performing service provisioning.

When routing new client traffic demands, the baseline provisioning framework described in [16] is utilized, which gives preference to using idle capacity in existing OChs and if new OChs need to be created prioritizes minimizing the number of new interfaces required, breaking ties by selecting the most spectral efficient solution. The three shortest paths are considered when searching for the best solution for a new OCh. Importantly, different criteria can be used to determine the feasibility of using a given modulation format over a specific path. We define the spectrum feasibility threshold (SFT) as the minimum share of frequency slots with RM larger or equal to 0 over the specific routing path to accept using the format. The SFT takes values 10%, 50%, and 100% in the analysis reported in Section IV. Note that a smaller SFT results in a more aggressive, i.e., close to the performance limit, provisioning, but may lead to increased vulnerability to power transients. Moreover, when multiple frequency slots have non-negative residual margin, the SA algorithm may give preference to the one with the smallest RM (Smallest-RM), the largest RM (Largest-RM) or the largest RM for 16QAM and smallest RM for all other formats (800G_Prio-RM).

D. Transient-impact Simulation

The framework described in the previous sub-section contains the building blocks required to assess key network-level metrics such as blocking probability and resource consumption (e.g., interface count). However, evaluating the impact of transients requires extending this framework with additional

Fig. 5: Transient-impact simulation workflow.

building blocks. Figure 5 shows the main steps for simulating link faults and characterizing the SRS-induced power transients in a SuperC+L-band or other MBT-based network.

After routing all traffic demands, the next steps are to (1) re-optimize the gain and tilt of the amplifiers, taking into account the current-state-of-life (CoL), i.e., the actual spectral occupation of each span, and (2) recompute the RM of each provisioned channel. This is required to replicate the network state exactly before simulating a failure.

Each link in the network is then failed (one independent simulation per link), which implies removing all channels traversing the spans of that link from the network. For each failure scenario, the $GSNR_i$ of each span not contained in the failed link is recomputed, taking into account the spectral occupation that results from the failure and assuming that the amplifiers' gain and tilt is kept unchanged (i.e., same as pre-fault, since control of the amplifiers is assumed to act at a longer time scale than the one being considered to evaluate the power transient). Finally, the RM of each channel not traversing the failed link is recomputed. Channels with negative RM in these conditions are susceptible to traffic disruption due to power transients.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first set of results evaluates the impact of the SFT value adopted during provisioning. Assuming MaxAv-GSNR EoL span optimization, 800G_Prio-RM SA and SFT-10%, SFT-50%, and SFT-100%, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 show the blocked and carried traffic load and the total interface count, respectively. As can be seen, enforcing a more aggressive SFT in provisioning reduces both blocked traffic load and interface count, which contributes to a reduction in capital expenditures. However, as can be observed in Fig. 8, which plots the worst-case reduction in RM experienced by each provisioned channel when considering all single link failure scenarios, a more aggressive SFT leads, on average, to more pronounced degradation of channels' RM due to power transients. The average fraction of provisioned channels that fail due to transients is 10.84% with SFT-10% and only 0.64% with SFT-

Fig. 6: Blocked and carried traffic load for different SFT.

Fig. 7: Total interface count for different SFT.

100%. The worst-case fraction (i.e., over all possible failures) is 20.87% and 3.27%, respectively.

The second set of simulation results considers the impact of the SA strategy. Assuming MaxAv-RM and SFT-10%, it is observed that approximately the same blocking probability and number of interfaces are obtained when enforcing Smallest-RM, Largest-RM, and 800G_Prio-RM (plots are omitted for the sake of space) to assign frequency slots to optical channels. Nevertheless, the SA strategy impacts the vulnerability to transients. For instance, the average fraction of provisioned channels that fail due to transients is reduced from 10.84% with 800G_Prio-RM (results are very similar with Smallest-RM) to 5.39% with Largest-RM. In contrast, the worst-case fraction decreases from 20.87% to 11.82%. Fig. 9 depicts the worst-case reduction in RM experienced by each provisioned channel for the three SA strategies. Although the curves are mostly overlapped, it can be seen that with Largest-RM, there are more channels with a worst-case variation of RM close to zero. Note that very small reductions of RM are less likely

Fig. 8: Worst-case channel RM variation for different SFT.

Fig. 9: Worst-case channel RM variation for different SA.

to result in a negative RM and consequent service disruption. Since no noticeable penalty in both blocking probability and interface count is observed, Largest- RM would be the most suitable SA strategy in this scenario.

The third set of results focuses on the impact of the span optimization criteria used to determine the amplifiers' gain and tilt. Assuming SFT-10% and 800G_Prio- RM , Fig. 10 presents the blocked and carried traffic load, whereas considering SFT-10% and SFT-100%, Fig. 11 shows the interface count. The results show distinct trends, with MaxLow-GSNR performing better when considering the blocked traffic load and MaxAv-GSNR outperforming it in interface count. The reason for this is that MaxLow-GSNR improves the worst performing frequency slots at the expense of reducing the GSNR of other frequency slots, decreasing the average GSNR. This slightly hampers reach, which increases the number of interfaces required to satisfy the set of traffic demands (Fig. 11). On the other hand, since a few extra 3R regenerators are used to bridge the reach gap, the average SE of deployed OChs

Fig. 10: Blocked and carried traffic load for different span optimization criteria.

Fig. 11: Total interface count for different span optimization criteria.

is slightly higher, which justifies the improvement in carried traffic load (Fig. 10). Fig. 12 plots the worst-case channel RM variation for both span optimization criteria. The curves clearly suggest that using MaxLow-GSNR span optimization results in an improved robustness to power transients. In fact, the average fraction of provisioned channels that fail due to transients is decreased from 10.84% with MaxAv-GSNR to only 1.61% with MaxLow-GSNR, whereas the worst-case fraction is reduced from 20.87% to 9.24%.

The final set of results considers imposing a limit on the number of links (hops) traversed by every provisioned OCh. Since the effect of power transients propagates downstream, by limiting the extension of OChs, it is possible to mitigate the impact of transients. Following this reasoning and based on the observation that the average hop count of established channels in the previous analysis varies between 4.5 and 5 hops, another set of simulations was performed assuming

Fig. 12: Worst-case channel RM variation for different span optimization criteria.

Fig. 13: Worst-case channel RM variation for different maximum hop count limits.

provisioning limited the number of hops used by OChs to 3 or 2. Fig. 13 shows the worst-case channel RM variation for the case with no explicit limit and for a maximum hop count of 3 and 2. The plot highlights the significant impact of limiting OCh hop count since it leads to a very steep reduction in the worst-case RM variation. Moreover, by reducing the OChs' length, their SE is also improved, which results in an increase of traffic load (for a reference blocking probability of 1%) of 67% and 87%, when adopting the 3 and 2 hop limit, respectively. However, these hop-count-limited solutions can be expensive to deploy. For instance, for an offered traffic load of 52 Tb/s they require increasing the number of interfaces used by 59% and 111% when imposing a 3-hop and 2-hop limit, respectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The SuperC+L-band can be exploited to increase capacity of current transport networks. However, their design and

operation must ensure robustness to the enhanced impact of SRS. This paper described a framework and presented results that give insight on how different network design and provisioning strategies fair in terms of both the vulnerability of established channels to SRS-induced power transients and the usable capacity and interface count requirements.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. J. Winzer *et al.*, "Fiber-optic transmission and networking: the previous 20 and the next 20 years [invited]," *Opt. Express*, vol. 26, no. 18, pp. 24 190–24 239, 2018.
- [2] A. Ferrari *et al.*, "Assessment on the achievable throughput of multi-band ITU-T G.652.D fiber transmission systems," *J. Lightwave Technol.*, vol. 38, no. 16, pp. 4279–4291, 2020.
- [3] Rob Shore, "Optical networking in 2024 - lighting the way forward," [Online]. Available: <https://www.thefastmode.com/expert-opinion/34436-optical-networking-in-2024-lighting-the-way-forward>.
- [4] A. Souza *et al.*, "Cost analysis of ultrawideband transmission in optical networks," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 81–93, 2024.
- [5] M. Cantono *et al.*, "Introducing the generalized GN-model for nonlinear interference generation including space/frequency variations of loss/gain," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1710.02225*, 2017.
- [6] A. Souza *et al.*, "Comparison of fast quality of transmission estimation methods for C + L + S optical systems," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 15, no. 11, pp. F1–F12, 2023.
- [7] —, "On the impact of fault-induced power transients in wideband optical networks," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2023*. Optica Publishing Group, 2023.
- [8] X. Zhao *et al.*, "Impact of WDM-band drop on S + C + L multi-band optical transmission systems," in *2023 Asia Communications and Photonics Conference/2023 International Photonics and Optoelectronics Meetings (ACP/POEM)*, 2023, pp. 1–5.
- [9] Srivastava *et al.*, "Fast-link control protection of surviving channels in multiwavelength optical networks," *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 9, no. 12, pp. 1667–1669, 1997.
- [10] A. P. Vela *et al.*, "BER degradation detection and failure identification in elastic optical networks," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 35, no. 21, pp. 4595–4604, 2017.
- [11] Paul Momtahan, "Meeting the 4 challenges of C+L," [Online]. Available: <https://www.infinera.com/blog/meeting-the-4-challenges-of-cl/>.
- [12] P. Poggiolini and Y. Jiang, "Recent advances in the modeling of the impact of nonlinear fiber propagation effects on uncompensated coherent transmission systems," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 458–480, 2017.
- [13] A. Ferrari *et al.*, "Experimental validation of an open source quality of transmission estimator for open optical networks," in *2020 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, 2020, pp. 1–3.
- [14] OpenZR+ MSA, "OpenZR+ specifications, version 3.0," [Online]. Available: https://openzrplus.org/site/assets/files/1096/openzrplus_rev3p0_final2.pdf.
- [15] The Institute of Electronics, Information and Communication Engineers (Technical Committee on Photonic Network), "Japan photonic network model (JPNM)," [Online]. Available: https://www.ieice.org/cs/pn/eng/jpnm_en.html.
- [16] J. Pedro and H. Bock, "Effectiveness of coherent pluggable interfaces in brownfield optical network deployments," in *2022 IEEE Latin-American Conference on Communications (LATINCOM)*, 2022.
- [17] B. Correia *et al.*, "Optical power control strategies for optimized C+L+S-bands network performance," in *2021 Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC)*, 2021, p. W1F.8.